

Energy – Momenta Relation

O Manor

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Introduction

The 8T is a variational curvature framework, which consists of one equation:

$$\frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s} \frac{\partial s}{\partial M_E} \frac{\partial M_E}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} - \frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s'} \frac{\partial s'}{\partial M_E} \frac{\partial M_E}{\partial g'} \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} = 0 \quad (1)$$

For fermions:

$$\sum_{i=1}^N \delta g_i = 0$$

For Bosons, we have discrete amount of net curvature, which is a subset of the original set that vanished into matter:

$$\left(\sum_{i=1}^m \delta g_i > 0 \right) \in \sum_{i=1}^N \delta g_i = 0$$

That construction yielded the primordial coupling constants series, which is covered in depth in the 8T thesis and proved that the Bosons are isomorphic to prime numbers as presented in the next page in equations (1.1) and (1.2). Which is covered in depth in the 8T thesis.

$$F_{V=0} = 8 + (1) \quad (1.1)$$

$$F_R \# = \left(8 * \prod_{V=1}^{V=R} N_V + (3) \right) + N_V = 30:128:850:9254.. \quad (1.2)$$

$$N_V = 2 \left(V + \frac{1}{2} \right); V \geq 0$$

$$N_V \in \mathbb{P} \cup (+1); \mathbb{P} \rightarrow \text{Set of Primes}$$

$$N_V = P_{max} \in [0, \mathbb{R}] \cup (+1); P_{max} \in \mathbb{P}$$

The two major themes of the 8T, are two symmetry breaks, that is mutation of the eight to two directions:

$$8 + (1) \cup 8 \prod_{V=1}^K N_V + K$$

$$K = 3 + N_{V=k..}$$

Which is the symmetry break of the gauge interactions. The second symmetry break is of mass, given by the decrease in order masses of the generation Fermions.

$$8 - (1)$$

Consider the Einstein relationship as presented in QFT, where the constants of Planck and c are normalized to one:

$$E^2 = p^2 + m^2$$

Which means:

$$E^2 - m^2 = p^2$$

The problem with this relation is the following: If one dives deeper and asks what exactly meant by the term "energy" is and what is meant by the term "mass", the relation and the theory is not able to answer it. Any theory that present terms which are not clearly defined is incomplete. To the author of the 8T, the Einstein relation is partial and insufficient, and thereby the same applies for the Klein Gordon equation. To solve the problem of those terms, the author used the mapping of Ricci curvature into Energy:

$$\varphi: g \rightarrow E$$

Such that the energy is taken to the Hamiltonian of the 8T:

$$E^2 \equiv \hat{H}$$

$$\hat{H} = \hat{T} + \hat{U}$$

$$\hat{T}_i = \frac{\partial^2 g'_i}{\partial t^2} = \frac{\partial g_i}{\partial t}; \forall s_{1 \rightarrow n}$$

$$\hat{U}_i = \sum_{i=1}^N \delta g_i; \forall s_{1 \rightarrow n}$$

Now according to the Einstein relation we can create an Iso-arrow between the variational curvature Hamiltonian and the latter. The momenta is isomorphic to the kinetic term of the 8T, and the mass is isomorphic to the arbitrary variations vanishing into matter.

The potential energy as matter is confined curvature which is not manifested da facto. That is the insertions:

$$\begin{aligned}\varphi^A: \hat{T}_i &\rightarrow p \\ \varphi^B: \hat{U}_i &\rightarrow m^2\end{aligned}$$

Meaning that the new Einstein relation describe energy as the summation of curvature diverging given by a kinetic energy, and the potential energy, which is curvature diverging or mass. Notice that the first mapping does not need to be squared at the kinetic term is already second power. Energy is the summation of converging and diverging curvature on the manifold, which are in inverse relation to each other and cancel each other out.

$$8 + (1) + 8 - (1) = 0$$

Moreover, the momenta is the sum of curvature minus the converging curvature. Mass is the sum of curvature minus the diverging curvature. The previously vague terms in the Einstein relation, within the new setting, are clearly defined.

The Graviton Decay

We have presented several forms to the formation of unseen particles, which contain higher spin and composed by several sub-elements. Since in particle physics it is not natural to compose particles, but rather to derive the nature of particle based on their decays, the author will make several predictions concerning a potential set of decays of the Graviton using the coupling term of spin two particle using the primordial coupling constants series. The first possible decay is the following.

$$G^{K=1} \rightarrow (\overline{e^-}) + (e^-) + \gamma + \gamma$$

The superscript is meant to indicate that infinite compositions are possible. It can be parametrized:

$$K \in \mathbb{R}$$

The arrows on the Electrons as during the decay they can not be combined or interact with each other. Each electron must appear with a distinct photon, such as the decay is coming to an agreement with the one of the terms describing Gravity in the 8T:

$$[(2N_{gravity}) + (\overline{3}) + (\overline{3})] + \gamma + \gamma \rightarrow [(2N_{gravity}) + (\overline{e^-}) + (e^-)] + \gamma + \gamma$$

Another two possible decays:

$$G^{K=2} \rightarrow (\overline{e^-}) + \gamma + \gamma + \gamma$$

$$G^{K=3} \rightarrow (\overline{e^-}) + (e^-) + (\overline{e^-}) + \gamma$$

Using the isomorphism between the Electron and the Boson of the Weak interaction given by the second coupling term:

$$[(\mathbf{8} \times \mathbf{3}) + (\mathbf{3})] + 3 \rightarrow \left[2N_1 + \frac{1}{2}\right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

$$(\mathbf{3}) = +3$$

$$(e^-) = (W^-)$$

$$G^{K=4} \rightarrow (W^-) + (W^-) + \gamma + \gamma$$

$$G^{K=5} \rightarrow (W^-) + (W^-) + (W^-) + \gamma$$

$$G^{K=6} \rightarrow (W^-) + \gamma + \gamma + \gamma$$

The options are infinite as each four Bosonic decay is indicating a spin two particle. That classification was used to predict the Higgs via two photons relation, given by the classification:

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Spin 0: $2N_0$ variations

Spin $\frac{1}{2}$: $2N_0 + 3$ variations

Spin 1: $2N_0 + 3 + N_V$ variations

Spin $N = 2N_0 + 3 + N_{V1} + N_{V2} \dots$ variations

Each Boson is in itself represented by half unit spin, as it is ever confined with the Electron; those spins add up to one. That is an additional indication that the additional Boson is a discrete amount of curvature. Therefore, any decay involving a fourfold multiple of Bosons is synonymous with spin-two particle decay, i.e. a "Graviton".

$$\frac{1}{2} \times 4n = xG^{K=1}$$

$$n, x \in \mathbb{R}$$

Galactic Bends

Using the 8T setting, taking into account that matter has no curvature appearing da facto, as proven by the arbitrary variation term of the main equation

$$\sum_{i=1}^N \delta g_i = 0$$

According to the author, the extremum bend on the matric is given by the probability of Bosonic propagation, which, as the variation cluster increase in size, so does the chance of the higher coupling terms to be physically manifested. As the first term of each coupling is an even term which assumed to vanish into matter. That is in contrast to the approach taken back in the day, which considered the invariant three to prevent the vanishing into matter of the even term. Therefore, those immense areas of matter are those in which there exist the higher probability of Bosonic emitting by Fermions. Those Bosons are net curvature on the matric, overall the summation of all the Bosons over the pure number and their kind is the measure of the bend galaxy has and the summation is the same curvature that is being flattened by the complimentary manifolds in the packet.

"Dark Matter" – Patterns

As suggested by the main equation of the 8T, the same form matter is being created in other manifolds as well.

$$\frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s_m} \frac{\partial s_m}{\partial M_E} \frac{M_E}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} \delta g_m - \frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s_n} \frac{\partial s_n}{\partial M_E} \frac{M_E}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} \delta g_n = 0$$

$$1 \leq m, n \leq k/2$$

The variational distributions are identical in size and different in configuration.

$$\sum_{m=1}^{K/2} \delta g_m \rightarrow \mathcal{R}^{s_1} \in [0,1]$$

$$\sum_{n=1}^{K/2} \delta g_n \rightarrow \mathcal{R}^{s_2} \in [0,1]$$

$$\mathcal{R}^{s_1} \neq \mathcal{R}^{s_2}$$

$$\sum_{m=1}^{K/2} \delta g_m \equiv \sum_{n=1}^{K/2} \delta g_n$$

The key point of this section is the following, despite the assumption of the different distributions per manifold; the general pattern must be identical and can serve as a source of prediction. That is, our manifold can serve as a sample manifold for a prediction.

If the amount of matter is more dense as one get closer to the center of galaxies in general, so does the amount of "dark matter" must increase at the same rate. In other words, the distributions patterns must be identical, as it is just matter from a distinct manifold flattening our own. The density of dark matter should be identical to the density of "regular matter" in "our galaxies" on this manifold.

Prediction (1): Dark matter density per volume must be identical to matter density on this galaxy.

Prediction (1.1): Dark matter should be more common in high-density areas across galaxies. As the distance from the core of the galaxies increase, dark matter density decrease. In other words dark matter amount should be inversely proportional to the distance from the core of the galaxy, assuming implicitly that the matter density in the core is higher than in the spirals.

Prediction (2): dark matter should be increased proportionally to time.

Manifold Sampling

Using the fact that the number of dimensions of other manifolds is not known, it is assumed to be identical as to create perfect flattening of manifold pairs. Assuming we know about dimensions of only one manifold, can we prove mathematically that there exist only one class of manifold, i.e. the Lorentz manifold with (3,1) signature? The author will attempt at proving just that. Assuming there exist two pairs of two manifolds per pair flattening each other:

$$\frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s_1} - \frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s_2} = \mathfrak{Z}_1$$

$$\mathfrak{Z}_1 + \mathfrak{Z}_2 = 0$$

Assuming we live on the first manifold, which has three dimensions, in order for the universe to be flat, the second complimentary manifold in the pair must be three-dimensional as well, or else one dimension will not get flattened. As those dimensions are composing the three dimensional volume of the manifold, and the volume must aspire zero as the manifold is getting flattened. Sounds counter intuitive but it is possible to claim that the volume decrease while the surface area of the manifold increases.

$$\left(\frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s_1} - \frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s_2} \right) + \left(\frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s_3} - \frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s_4} \right) = 0$$

Now take the second pair of universe and replace our manifold with the corresponding first manifold in the pair.

$$\frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s_1} \rightarrow \frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s_3}$$

$$\frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s_3} \rightarrow \frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s_1}$$

Such that:

$$\left(\frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s_3} - \frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s_2}\right) + \left(\frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s_1} - \frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s_4}\right) = 0$$

Now the fourth manifold must be three dimensional, and according to the original construction and this construction so does the third. The third as to be three dimensional due to the second being three dimensional as a result of the first manifold, "our manifold" being three dimensional. So in a sense our manifold can be used as a sample manifold that each other manifold pair which create an endless set of identical manifolds in their dimension count, each manifold with a unique arrow and a unique flattening moment. The stationarity condition is imposing a restriction on the manifolds. That is, if the number of dimensions is different, those manifolds will not be stationary, i.e. flat, as dimensions are related to volume. Therefore, by knowing the number of dimensions on one manifold, and constructing distinct manifold pairs using the same manifold, i.e. sampling one manifold over the set of pairs, it is possible to mathematically derive, if one is correct, the fact that the sampled pairs universes due to one manifold must be identical in dimensions to our own manifold. Now there exist four manifolds which can be sampled and the rate of sampling is fourfold compared to one manifold. Which is coming to an agreement with the \mathcal{L} theorem of the 8T, nature is creating extremums on objects and classes, and in particular aspire to minimize their class and while maximizing the number of objects within that class. As a result of the construction there exist an even number of finite dimensional manifolds of the same kind. Each manifold proven three-dimensional can serve as a "sample manifold" after compared with our own. In a way it is an endless process, and a full proof will never be attained as the number of manifold is infinite, but using the algorithm of manifold samples set which also increase at a rapid rate, so it is possible to proof that a smaller infinity of manifolds is identical to our own.

References

- [1] O. Manor. "8 Theory – The Theory of Everything" In: (2021)

M. Okad@Theory